

Hypothetical Velocity and Photon Ray Theory for Reflection/Refraction from a Moving Surface

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 19, 2023

In (1) we outlined a procedure using a hypothetical velocity H which acted as a hypotenuse (along the x axis for refraction with a medium interface along the x axis) whose projection yields $c/n(i)$ (along the photon ray direction) in each medium, where $n(i)$ is the index of refraction. This approach may also be used for reflection from a moving medium interface. Thus, one may combine the two and have reflection/refraction from a moving medium interface. The hypothetical velocity H is the same in each medium. Here we extend the result of (1) for refraction in a medium with a moving interface. (We show that the hypothetical velocity approach may be used to describe both reflection and refraction from a moving interface of media of refractions, i.e. a surface along the x axis, moving with velocity v , such that one has n_1 above and n_2 below. A photon ray making an angle AA with the y -axis both reflects and refracts, and the hypothetical velocity approach describes both.

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In (2), a photon ray theory is presented to deal with the same problem. In this case, conserved quantities are associated with energy and momentum and not a hypothetical velocity, but both approaches yield the same result as we show.

We try to show that the two approaches are identical and based on conservation, although they involve looking at the problem in different ways.

Hypothetical Velocity

In (1) we introduced a hypothetical velocity H approach which uses a constant (conserved) H which in the case of refraction lies along the x axis, the same axis as the medium interface. This is also the axis of the conserved momentum component. (This is an important feature.)

An incident ray moves at an angle AA with the y axis and refracts with an angle BB (measured from the y axis) in the second medium. The hypothetical velocity is the same in both media and acts as a hypotenuse, even though it is along the x -axis. In each medium one may find the projection of H along the photon ray path which yields its velocity. In particular:

$$H \cos(90-AA) = c/n_1 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad H \cos(90-BB) = c/n_2 \quad ((1b))$$

Thus: $\sin(AA) / \sin(BB) = n_2/n_1$ Snell's law. ((2))

We note that even though H is conserved (in each medium) and lies along the x axis, there is no mention of energy or momentum for the photon. These, however, are linked by $E = |p| (c/n_i)$. If E is the same in both media, then $p(\text{incident}) = p n_1$ and $p(\text{refracted}) = p n_2$.

We argued in (1) that the hypothetical velocity may also be applied to a moving mirror in order to describe reflection. In this case, there is again a conserved hypothetical velocity along the x -axis. The mirror moves along the y -axis with velocity v , so one may find its component along

both the incident ray and the reflected one. $H \cos(90-AA)$ and $H \cos(90-BB)$ then represent the relative speeds along the incident and reflected rays, where H is conserved and along the x -axis. For the incident ray, one uses $-v$ and for the reflected v so:

$$\sin(AA) / \sin(BB \text{ (reflect)}) = (c-v\cos(AA)) / (c+v\cos(BB)) \quad ((3))$$

At this point, we wish to point out the following issue related to conservation of momentum parallel to the medium interface along the x axis. If one only has reflection, as in the case of a moving mirror, then AA refers to the incident photon ray and BB to the reflected and the index of refraction is the same for the incident and reflected.

Consider instead of a moving mirror, a medium interface which moves along the y -axis, while lying along the x . This problem is presented in (2). In such a case, there should be both reflection and refraction. It seems reflection should be the same as in the case of a moving mirror. The hypothetical velocity approach H yields ((3)). The hypothetical velocity, however, has also been used to describe refraction. In such a case ((3)) should hold for refraction, but with a modification of the speeds of light in ((3)), i.e.

$$\sin(AA) / \sin(BB(\text{refract})) = (c/n1-v\cos(AA)) / (c/n2+v\cos(BB)) \quad ((4))$$

The hypothetical velocity approach yields results for both reflection and refraction. For the refraction case, one sees that neither energy nor momentum appear. To introduce energy, one may use $E = |p| c/n$. ((6))

In the case of refraction, one has conservation of momentum along the surface of the medium, so:

$$|p(\text{incident})| \sin(AA) = |p(\text{refracted})| \sin(BB) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Using ((6)) yields: } E(\text{incident}) n1 \sin(AA) = E(\text{refracted}) n2 \sin(BB) \quad ((8))$$

In (2), ((8)) is called a generalized Snell's law. ((8)) may then be used in ((4)) to yield:

$$E(\text{incident}) / E(\text{refracted}) = (1 - (v/c)n1 \cos(AA)) / (1 + (v/c)n2 \cos(BB)) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is also presented in (2) using a different approach (photon ray theory).

Thus the hypothetical velocity approach which does not use E or p explicitly may be used to find an expression with $E(\text{incident})$ and $E(\text{refracted})$. The reflected ray equation ((3)) does not seem to be given in (2), but is used in (1) and modified here to include refraction.

Photon Ray Theory

In (2) photon ray theory is used to describe the refraction of an incident photon making an angle AA with the y axis and encountering an interface, lying along the x-axis, which moves along the y axis with constant velocity v. This theory differs from the hypothetical velocity one in that it deals explicitly with energy and momentum.

The approach of ((2)) is to define:

$$F = (r(\text{vector}) - v \text{ dot } p') \quad ((10))$$

Here v is the velocity of the moving interface with p' vector = p vector. Then:

$$p = p' \text{ vector} = dF/dr \text{ vector} \quad \text{and} \quad r' \text{ vector} = dF/dk \text{ vector} = r \text{ vector} - v (\text{vector}) t \quad ((11))$$

Here p and p' vector refer to a math transform, i.e. p vector = p' vector and r' vector = r vector - v (vector) t.

((2)) argues that the new Hamiltonian for ' is:

$$E' = E + dF/dt \text{ partial} = E - v \text{ dot } p' \quad ((12))$$

E' is argued to be a constant of motion and a second constant of motion is introduced, which is the component of momentum along the interface surface. This second conservation law is already known independently of both the hypothetical velocity and photon ray theory approaches.

One may note that E - v dot p appears in the phase of the photon wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + ip \text{ dot } r) = \exp(it (-E + p \text{ dot } dr/dt))$. Thus, the conservation argument seems to be a kind of constant phase one, where $-E + p \text{ dot } v$ is a constant.

$V \text{ dot } p' = v \text{ dot } p = |v| |p| \cos(AA)$ where AA is the angle between the photon ray and the y axis. Given conservation of ((12)) and using $E = |p| c/n$ one has:

$$E(\text{refracted}) / E(\text{reflected}) = (1 - (v/c) n1 \cos(AA)) / (1 + (v/c) n2 \cos(BB)) \quad ((13))$$

Here AA is the incident photon ray angle with the y-axis and BB the refracted, also with the y axis. One sees that ((13)) contains the energy variable and is equivalent to the hypothetical velocity result combined with conservation of momentum along the interface surface, i.e. ((9)).

In the case of hypothetical velocity H, which lies along the x axis, which is the same axis as the conserved component of momentum, one may use strictly hypothetical velocity conservation (using H as a hypotenuse which yields ray velocity) to obtain an equation linking AA and BB with no E or |p| appearing.

The approach of (2) is to use a conservation equation involving energy, namely ((12)). One may note, however, that $E - v \cdot p = E - |v| \cos(AA) |p|$ and $E = |p| c/n$, so the conserved quantity E' is equivalent to: $E(1 - |v|/n/c)$. Thus:

$$E(\text{incident}) / E(\text{refracted}) = (1 - v n_1/c \cos(AA)) / (1 + v n_2/c \cos(BB)) \quad ((13))$$

Now, $v \cdot p$ is both the component of v parallel to p and vice versa. If one considers the former, then $1 - v \cdot (p \text{ unit vector}) n/c \rightarrow c/n - v(\text{along } p)$ which is a relative velocity. Also:

$$E(\text{incident}) / E(\text{refracted}) = |p \text{ incident}| c/n_1 / (|p \text{ refracted}| c/n_2) \quad ((14))$$

$|p \text{ incident}|$ and $|p \text{ refracted}|$, however, appear in another conservation law, namely the component of momentum along the interface surface, which involves $|p \text{ incident}| \sin(AA)$ and $|p \text{ refracted}| \sin(BB)$. Thus one may introduce $\sin(AA)$ and $\sin(BB)$ angles. These correspond to the same H along the momentum conservation axis projected as a hypotenuse along this axis, onto the actual ray axis, using the angle $90-AA$, i.e. $\cos(90-AA)$ which equals $\sin(AA)$. Thus we argue that the hypothetical velocity approach is equivalent to the photon ray one. One may see why the hypothetical velocity lies along the same axis as the conserved component of momentum and how this links the two approaches (i.e. hypothetical velocity and photon ray theory).

Conclusion

In (1) we introduced a hypothetical velocity H which lies along the axis of the conserved momentum component for both a static refraction and moving mirror problem. H is conserved and acts as a hypotenuse. Its projection along the photon ray, namely $H \cos(90-AA)$ where AA is an angle with the y -axis for a mirror medium interface along x , is equal to the velocity or relative velocity along the photon ray axis. The latter case applies to a moving mirror. One may then calculate $H \cos(90-AA)$ for the incident ray and $H \cos(90-BB)$ for a reflected or refracted ray and then link the two because H is the same. We show here that this approach may be used for both reflection and refraction from an interface along the x axis moving along the y axis with a speed v .

In (2), a photon ray approach is used which yields the same result, but is based on conservation of an energy $E' = E - v \cdot p$ where E is the actual energy, v the velocity of the moving mirror and p momentum with $E = |p| c/n$. We show that not only does this approach yield the same result as the hypothetical velocity one, but that both are identical.

We further note that the conservation of $E - v \cdot p$ seems to follow from the photon wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r) = \exp(-it(E - p \cdot dr/dt))$ where dr/dt is taken to be a velocity in the problem, namely that of the moving interface of media. Thus, both the hypothetical velocity and photon ray approaches seem to follow from the photon wavefunction phase being constant.

References

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